

STEPS IN TEACHING SPEAKING.

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What steps are involved in speaking? Think about conversation that you have with your friends or family. What do you do before you say something? When we talk our friend in our native language our brains think quickly and easily. We don't notice that speaking is very complicated. However when we speak a foreign language, it takes us much longer to talk. This is because speaking is composed of many steps. To speak we do the following:

1. Listen and understand other people.
2. Have an idea and want to express it.
3. Remember vocabulary which can express this idea.
4. Use grammar correctly.
5. Pronounce the words understandably.

Speaking is an active skill. Speakers think of everything themselves, the ideas, the words, the grammar. Finally all of the words and grammar must be pronounced clearly. This is much more difficult than listening. No wonder speaking English is so difficult, Using recitation to practice speaking is wrong. It doesn't practice the skills students will need to speak English fluently. When students practice speaking in the classroom, they should do the steps which are part of speaking. They need to think of original ideas, remember words and use grammar themselves. Speaking which resemble real communication prepare students better for speaking outside in the classroom. How to create real speaking in the classroom. Even if teachers are ready to practice speaking the lessons will not be successful unless the students themselves want to talk. But how can teachers make students want to talk. We need to choose interesting, useful and fun themes for our lessons. Remember that students love to talk about themselves and their opinions, their hobbies and their families. Students like to play games in English. They also enjoy using their imagination to create situations. What would they say on an English singers or actors or the president of America? The best speaking activities have one or more of these elements an opportunity for students to talk about themselves, a chance to use English as a game, or a time to fantasize about a story or situation.

Good speaking activities also resemble real world conversations. They require students to find out information by asking questions and listening to the answers. In this way they communicate with their groupmates and you their teacher. Students use English to describe a situation which has meaning for them. This shows students the context for words. Thus they learn that a word is more than letters on paper, it has a meaning and other words associated with it. Using words within a context helps students remember vocabulary and use words correctly. Communicative speaking activities often have tasks which make students talk about themselves, their ideas, or a situation within the classroom. There are three main kinds of communicative activities: opinion gap activities, information gap activities and guessing games. Within these activities, someone has information which other students need to complete a task. This situation creates “communicative need”. Communicative need means students have a reason to communicate with each other. Students listen and speak to each other to complete the task successfully. Students exchange personal information about themselves in opinion gap activities. They interview each other using words which they are learning in class. For example if your class is learning about professions they can discuss their family jobs. While interview each other they fill in a chart. After they are finished interviewing their partner you discuss the answers. Students who are good at English can also use it by taking more difficult topics. Students exchange information about other topic in information gap activities. In these activities one student has information that the other student needs. For example half of the students are given a piece of paper with information. The students in the other group should interview them and by this way they can learn their information. When they are finished asking questions they may look at the paper to see if their answers are correct. Guessing games are the most interesting communicative activities for students. In these games students guess the answer to a puzzle. The teacher writes some names which are interesting for students to pieces of paper and puts them on his table. The papers are face-down so students cannot see the words. One student comes to the front, choses a paper, but keeps the name of the word a secret. Student describes the word and others try to guess it. Students often make mistakes when they talk. We shouldn't interrupt them while speaking. If we stop them every time they make mistake, they will never learn to say a full sentence. After your student finish you can say that sentence with the same mistake, and ask the student to find that mistake. It will be very helpful. Ask students to repeat the correct form. Sometimes students speak incorrectly because they haven't learned the right grammar to use. Explaining this kind of mistake might take too much time. You

don't have to correct it. You can ignore it. Later you can explain the grammar rules once more. One of the best ways to deal with mistakes is to prevent them. Good speakers are also good listeners. Listening and speaking skills depend on each other. Speaking activities are almost always good listening activities.

The communication between the student and the teacher serves as a connection between the two, which provides a better atmosphere for a classroom environment. Of course a teacher is not going to understand every problem for every student in his or her classroom, but will acquire enough information for speaking for those students who are struggling with specific tasks. A significant body of research indicates that "academic achievement and student behavior are influenced by the quality of the teacher and student relationship. The more the teacher connects or communicates with his or her students, the more likely they will be able to help students speak at a high level and accomplish quickly.

The teacher needs to understand that students have different character and different abilities backgrounds. A teacher then needs to understand the value of the students' self-concepts, which can be of greater value and build self-worth for minority students. If the teacher demonstrates an understanding of the student's concept, it will provide a better understanding between the teacher and the student. Therefore, those teachers who demonstrate respect towards their students, automatically win favor by having active learners in their classroom. The arrogant or offensive teacher will lack these positive qualities due to his or her lack of control over the students. Teachers should assert that they should also be treated with respect and their responsibilities to ensure that students speak each other with kindness. According to the Jones, "teachers are encouraged to blend their warmth and firmness towards the students in their classroom, but with realistic limits"

Speaking occurs best when:

- *There is a respect between teacher and student.
- *It is self-directed. Adults can share responsibility for their own learning, because they know their own needs.
- * It is participative. Participation in the learning process is active not passive.
- *It provides feedback. Effective learning provides feedback that is corrective but supportive.
- *It provides a safe atmosphere. Cheerful, relaxed person learns more easily than who is fearful, embarrassed or angry.

REFERENCES:

1. Tursunboyeva L. T. THE TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL MATERIALS //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 41-44.
2. Tursunboyeva L. T. THE TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL MATERIALS //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 41-44.
3. Tukhtamuradovna T. L. VARIETY OF METHODS IN TEACHING //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 557-558.
4. Tursunboyeva L. T. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF A PERSONALITY OF A STUDENT //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 133-140.
5. Richard I. Arends “Learning to teach” Second edition. 2000
6. Kate M. Donley Teaching Real World English with multi-purpose speaking activities.